

Radio sirens: inferring H_0 with binary black holes and neutral hydrogen in the era of the Einstein Telescope and the SKA Observatory

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ABSTRACT

A new synergy between gravitational waves (GWs) and the study of the large-scale structure of the Universe is now emerging. Along this line of research, we combine simulated observations of stellar-origin black hole mergers and neutral hydrogen 21 cm line intensity mapping to probe the expansion rate of the Universe through the distance-redshift relation. GW signals from binary black holes provide direct distance information, while neutral hydrogen intensity maps offer a tomographic view of the large-scale structure of the Universe. Using the 3-dimensional density fields of hydrogen as a redshift prior for GW events, we explore a novel dark-sirens-like approach, here termed *radio sirens*, to measure the late-time expansion history of the Universe. We study the performance of the next-generation GW observatories, such as the Einstein Telescope, to ensure enough statistics and access to high-redshift data. On the other hand, future spectroscopic intensity mapping surveys with the SKA-Mid telescope are expected to trace the underlying dark matter distribution at large scales up to redshift $z \sim 3$. This combined methodology allows us to constrain the Hubble constant to $\sim 8\%$ precision, using around 3,000 GW events with signal-to-noise ratios greater than 150. This corresponds to an improvement of around 90% compared to not considering the information from the neutral hydrogen maps.

Key words: gravitational waves – large-scale structure of Universe – cosmological parameters

1 INTRODUCTION

Gravitational waves (GWs) have recently joined the cosmological scene, acting as standard sirens. They provide a direct measurement of the luminosity distance to the source, circumventing the calibration problems of more traditional probes such as standard candles (Schutz 1986; Holz & Hughes 2005). Inference on cosmological parameters requires independent measurements of luminosity distance and redshift. Even though we have distance information, to extract

cosmological information from GWs, we also need redshift information. The most straightforward way is represented by the so-called *bright sirens* (Markovic 1993; Dalal et al. 2006; Abbott et al. 2017; Chen et al. 2018; Feeney et al. 2019; Palmese et al. 2020a; Mancarella et al. 2024; Cozzumbo et al. 2025), where the host galaxy is uniquely identified, and its redshift is measured electromagnetically. This requires that the gravitational event is accompanied by its electromagnetic (EM) counterpart. This latter needs at least one neutron star to be involved in the merger, and so far, we have only detected one such bright siren event (Abbott et al. 2017). Without an EM counterpart, GW cosmology relies on inferring the redshift in-

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formation from the source-frame mass distribution, the *spectral siren* method (Chernoff & Finn 1993; Taylor & Gair 2012; You et al. 2021; Ye & Fishbach 2021; Ezquiaga & Holz 2022; Mastroianni et al. 2023; Ferraiuolo et al. 2025; Magaña Hernandez & Palmese 2025; Pierra & Papadopoulos 2026; Tagliacucchi et al. 2026; Bertheas et al. 2026). In this case, a model of the astrophysical mass distribution is needed, whereas what is measured is the detector-frame mass of each event. In addition to the information from the mass modeling, constraints come from galaxy catalogs, where each galaxy represents a possible host of the GW source.

In the context of *dark sirens*, galaxy catalogs have been considered in two possible ways. The first is to use them to reconstruct a galaxy density profile, referred to as a line-of-sight (LoS) redshift prior (Gray et al. 2023), and then statistically allocate GW sources more likely in overdensities of this profile. This type of approach is usually referred to as the “galaxy catalog” method (Schutz 1986; Holz & Hughes 2005; MacLeod & Hogan 2008; Del Pozzo 2012; Nishizawa 2017; Chen et al. 2018; Fishbach et al. 2019; Soares-Santos et al. 2019; Gray et al. 2020; Palmese et al. 2020b; Abbott et al. 2021; Finke et al. 2021; Abbott et al. 2023; Mancarella et al. 2022; Gair et al. 2023; Gray et al. 2023; Borghi et al. 2024; Bom et al. 2024; Borghi et al. 2025). The second is to use summary statistics for the GWs and galaxies, such as the cross and auto angular power spectra (Oguri 2016; Bera et al. 2020; Mukherjee et al. 2021; Diaz & Mukherjee 2022; Scelfo et al. 2022; Mukherjee et al. 2024; Mali & Essick 2025; Ferri et al. 2025; Pedrotti et al. 2025; Santiago de Matos et al. 2025; Dalang et al. 2026). This method is typically referred to as the “cross-correlation” method. These two methods are actually two sides of the same method, and can be unified under some assumptions (Cheng & Gair 2026).

In this paper, we investigate the synergy between binary black hole (BBH) standard sirens as would be measurable with the Einstein Telescope (ET) and a neutral hydrogen (HI) intensity mapping (IM) survey with the SKA Observatory (SKAO) (Weltman 2020). We use a hybrid approach between the “cross-correlation” and “galaxy catalog” methods, where the density contrasts of HI calculated from the large-scale structure (LSS) are used to build the LoS redshift priors for the GW signals. Via the measurement of the redshifted 21 cm line, SKA-Mid, the SKAO radio telescope in South Africa, can potentially map, in single-dish mode, the LSS, covering an unprecedented sky area of 20,000 deg² up to $z \sim 3$ (SKA Cosmology SWG 2020). HI IM, with the one-to-one correspondence between the redshift of emission of the 21 cm signal and the observed frequency, offers a spectroscopic view of the matter distribution over the redshift interval in which GW distance measurements are available, providing an advantage over photometric galaxy catalog *dark siren* methods. This emerging technique is advancing fast thanks to purpose built telescopes as CHIME¹ and HIRAX² and to a large observational campaign carried out with the SKA-Mid precursor MeerKAT³. MeerKAT’s Large Area Synoptic Survey (MeerKLASS) (Santos et al. 2017) will reach a survey area of $\sim 10,000$ deg², up to $z \sim 1.4$ (Cunnington et al. 2026), and the field has already achieved successful calibration (Wang et al. 2021) and cosmological detections (Cunnington et al. 2023; MeerKLASS Collaboration et al. 2025).

Previous works (Scelfo et al. 2022; Zazzera et al. 2026) focused on GW and HI summary statistics, such as the angular power spectrum (see also Schulz et al. nd, *in preparation*). Here we focus on connect-

ing LSS to the number density of compact binary coalescence (CBC) mergers: using the 3-dimensional density fields of HI measured with radio telescopes to model the LoS redshift prior for GW events, we explore a dark-sirens-like approach, that we term *radio sirens*, to measure the late-time expansion history of the Universe. A similar approach combining GWs and HI temperature maps is also being explored in (Nanadoumgar-Lacroze et al. nd, *in preparation*).

Our goal is to isolate and quantify the constraining power of HI data. To this aim, we do not include any information from the BBH mass spectrum. This allows us to avoid any dependence on a specific mass model. Our primary result is therefore a comparison of the H_0 posterior obtained with and without incorporating HI maps in the LoS modeling at the inference stage.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we describe the construction of the mock HI maps and the GW simulations, and the hierarchical Bayesian analysis framework. In Section 3, we present the inferred posteriors for the Hubble parameter under different assumptions and setups. In Section 4, we discuss the implications, limitations, and future extensions of the proposed method.

2 METHODS

It can be assumed that both the HI field (Santos et al. 2015; Bull et al. 2016) and BBH mergers (Scelfo et al. 2018; Pedrotti et al. 2025) are biased tracers of the dark matter (DM) density field. This means that we can generally express the density contrast of a given tracer of the underlying DM density field as:

$$\delta_{\text{tracer}}(z, \text{RA}, \text{Dec}) = b_{\text{tracer}}(z)\delta_{\text{DM}}(z, \text{RA}, \text{Dec}), \quad (1)$$

where δ_{tracer} is the density contrast of the tracer, being it either HI or GWs, and δ_{DM} represents the DM density contrast. The couple RA and Dec define the direction in the sky. b_{tracer} is the bias parameter, with b_{HI} for HI and b_{GW} for GWs. Note that we are working under the simplified assumption that the bias is a function of redshift only.

If BBH mergers preferentially occur in overdense regions, then, since we do not have direct access to DM field distribution, the observed HI density can be used as an informative prior on the redshift of GW events. This gives us the distance-redshift relation needed for cosmological inference. Building on this idea, we develop a proof-of-concept *radio siren* framework and test how much HI tomography can improve constraints on cosmological parameters, particularly the Hubble constant. This is done in the context of the planned third-generation (3G) GW detectors, with the ET exemplifying the future gravitational interferometers’ capabilities, to ensure sufficient statistics and redshift reach. In this section, we begin by explaining how we build simulated radio observations of HI intensity maps, then how we connect them to the CBC merger rate, and how we simulate the mock GW data. Finally, we describe how the simulated radio and GW data are combined within a coherent analysis framework to infer cosmological parameters.

2.1 Building DM maps

Our starting point is the simulation of the DM distribution. Given that SKA-Mid frequency coverage will allow tomography of the 21 cm line of HI up to $z \sim 3$ and ET can trace BBHs up to even $z \sim 100$ (Branchesi et al. 2023; Abac et al. 2026), we set our analysis for $z \in [0, \sim 3]$.

We construct mock LSS maps starting from DM halo catalogs derived from the Dark Energy and Massive Neutrino Universe (DEMNUi) set of simulations (Castorina et al. 2015; Carbone

¹ <https://chime-experiment.ca/>

² <https://hirax.ukzn.ac.za/>

³ <https://www.sarao.ac.za/science/meerkat/>

et al. 2016; Parimbelli et al. 2022) in their high-resolution configuration (HR-DEMNUi, Hernández-Molinero et al. 2024; Verza et al. 2024). These simulations have been produced using the Gadget-3 code (Springel 2005). They are characterized by a Planck 2013 (Ade et al. 2014) baseline flat Λ cold dark matter (CDM) cosmology with different values of the total neutrino mass and of the parameters characterizing the dark energy (DE) equation of state (EoS). Our model considers only the massless neutrino flat CDM case and a box with side length of $500 \text{ Mpc } h^{-1}$ in comoving coordinates, with 2048^3 DM particles. A full-sky lightcone with three-dimensional geometry from redshift $z = 0$ to redshift $z \approx 8$ is then built, corresponding to a total comoving volume of approximately $3 \times 10^3 \text{ Gpc}^3 h^{-3}$. The approach used to build this lightcone, originally developed for weak lensing applications (Carbone et al. 2008; Calabrese et al. 2015; Hilbert et al. 2020), preserves the continuity of the gravitational potential across transverse directions. The lightcone volume is partitioned into concentric spherical shells of fixed comoving thickness, within which simulation outputs are coherently translated and rotated. Around 39 billion haloes are identified through the friend-of-friends (FoF) algorithm.

From the DM halo catalogs, we construct sky maps in redshift shells by counting the number of DM halos per pixel and converting these counts into overdensity maps:

$$\text{map}(z, \text{pix}_i) = \frac{N(z, \text{pix}_i) - \bar{N}_{\text{pix}}(z)}{\bar{N}_{\text{pix}}(z)}, \quad (2)$$

with

$$\bar{N}_{\text{pix}}(z) = \frac{1}{n_{\text{pix}}} \sum_i N(z, \text{pix}_i) \quad (3)$$

where $N(z, \text{pix})$ is the number count at a given redshift shell and pixel, $\bar{N}_{\text{pix}}(z)$ is the averaged number count per redshift shell, and n_{pix} is the total number of pixels, given the adopted resolution (see Sec. 2.3). pix_i represents the direction in the sky (RA, Dec). We adopt a Healpy (Górski et al. 2005; Zonca et al. 2019) pixelization with $\text{nside}=16$, which roughly corresponds to a resolution of $\sim 13 \text{ deg}^2$ per pixel. The binning in redshift, instead, follows approximately an equally-spaced distribution in the logarithm of the scale factor $a = (1+z)^{-1}$. This stems from the spherical shells partition of the lightcone as described above.

In building the DM density maps, we make the simplified assumption that haloes describe the DM background field. Even though this assumption is strong, we have verified that at the scales we inspect and for the exploratory purpose of this work, it does not affect our final conclusions.

2.2 Radio observations of neutral hydrogen

In this section, we build mock H_I radio observations starting from the DM maps generated in Sec. 2.1.

The 21 cm line of H_I rest-frame frequency ν_{21} is redshifted to lower frequencies due to cosmic expansion according to

$$\nu_{\text{obs}} = \nu_{21}/(1+z), \quad \text{with } \nu_{21} = 1420 \text{ MHz} \quad (4)$$

so that each instrumental frequency band can be directly mapped to a corresponding redshift interval.

The 21 cm line emission from H_I is a faint signal and it can be observed in emission from individual sources only at low redshift. By giving up on resolution and integrating the signal from multiple objects, IM allows instead to map the LSS at unprecedented depths (e.g. Battye et al. 2013; Kovetz et al. 2017). IM surveys with the radio

Figure 1. Horizon plots (*in magenta*) for the ET observations compared to the SKAO reach in redshift. The horizon represents the maximum redshift for CBC equal-mass and optimally oriented GW sources observed with a threshold SNR. Here we compare the standard SNR = 8 threshold (*dashed line*), with the one we use throughout this work, i.e. SNR = 150 (*solid line*). On the *x-axis* is the total source-frame mass of the binary, while on *y-axis* is the redshift of the merger. We used the triangular configuration for ET with the full cryogenic sensitivity curve available [here](#). The SKAO redshift ranges are highlighted horizontally in *purple*: there are the two bands of SKA-Mid, band 2 (950–1760 MHz) and band 1 (350–1050 MHz), and the high-redshift SKA-Low band (50–350 MHz). The intersection region of the two SKA-Mid bands is marked with two different hatches. In this work, we focus on both bands of SKA-Mid.

telescopes are thus capable of tracing the underlying DM distribution at large scales up to high redshift.

The SKAO will consist of two instruments, SKA-Low in Australia covering the band 50 – 350 MHz and SKA-Mid in South Africa, observing in band 2 (950–1760 MHz) and band 1 (350–1050 MHz). The SKAO observational bands are illustrated in Fig. 1, along with their corresponding redshift ranges. The figure highlights the synergy between SKAO and ET investigated in this work. Further details about GWs are provided in Sec. 2.3.

Using SKA-Mid in single-dish mode, it will thus be possible to measure the LSS up to $z \sim 3$ (SKA Cosmology SWG 2020), covering a much larger cosmological volume than possible with current SKA precursor observations.

As a first approximation, we assume a one-to-one correspondence between the H_I distribution and the DM field. In fact, as shown in Eq. 1, we can set the H_I bias parameter b_{H_I} to one with respect to the DM density contrast δ_{DM} . Moreover, we make the simplified assumption that we can work with full-sky coverage.

We obtain the H_I intensity maps from Eq. 2, setting $b_{\text{H}_I} = 1$, using the same sky resolution and redshift binning of the DM maps. This translates to a minimum frequency resolution above the MHz, larger than the instrumental capabilities of SKA-Mid. We show example maps at two different reference redshifts later on in Fig. 2 (Sec. 2.3) in connection with GW observations.

Note that what is effectively observed with H_I IM surveys is the temperature brightness in each pixel, which depends on the total H_I density as a function of redshift, Ω_{H_I} (Battye et al. 2013; Crighton et al. 2015; Péroux & Howk 2020). We assume this function is known and directly use the H_I density fluctuations for the analyses presented here.

Another approximation we make is not to explicitly include the chromatic beam response that would result from using SKA-Mid

in single-dish mode (Santos et al. 2015; SKA Cosmology SWG 2020). Given that we work with $n_{\text{side}}=16$ (see Sec. 2.2), the worst smoothing due to the beam (associated with the lower SKA-Mid frequency available and corresponding to redshift 3 in terms of the 21 cm line) is lower than the pixel resolution and therefore is not relevant for our settings.

Finally, we do not account for any systematics in the H_I maps or for the effect of foreground cleaning (e.g. Spinelli et al. 2021). Some of the H_I systematics and limited coverage of the maps will be addressed in (Nanadoumgar-Lacroze et al. nd, in preparation).

These assumptions define an optimistic baseline scenario. In realistic applications, deviations from these conditions are expected and may degrade or bias cosmological constraints. Quantifying all these effects in more detail is deferred to future work.

2.3 Mock GW data

To connect GWs with the underlying DM field, we need to parametrize the CBC merger rate as a function of the DM density contrast. We model the merger rate as the number of CBC sources, N_{CBC} , per redshift z , detector-frame time t and sky position Ω as

$$\frac{dN_{\text{CBC}}}{dz dt d\Omega} = \frac{dN_{\text{CBC}}}{dM_{\text{BH}} dt_{\text{src}}} \frac{1}{1+z} \frac{dM_{\text{BH}}}{dz d\Omega}, \quad (5)$$

where M_{BH} is the mass of available compact objects in binaries, and t_{src} is the time in the source frame. The first term describes the source-frame merger rate per available black hole (BH) mass, the second term is the distribution of binaries in redshift and angular position.

We parameterize the source-frame merger-rate term using a modified Madau-Dickinson model (Madau & Dickinson 2014),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dN_{\text{CBC}}}{dM_{\text{BH}} dt_{\text{src}}} &= R_{\text{BH}} \psi(z | \gamma, \kappa, z_p) \\ &= R_{\text{BH}} \left[1 + (1+z_p)^{-\gamma-\kappa} \right] \frac{(1+z)^\gamma}{1 + \left[\frac{1+z}{1+z_p} \right]^{\gamma+\kappa}} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\psi(z | \gamma, \kappa, z_p)$ is the Madau–Dickinson redshift evolution, and R_{BH} is the rate of mergers per year per solar mass available of compact objects. The overall merger rate acts as a multiplicative factor for the number density of BBH mergers. $\psi(z | \gamma, \kappa, z_p)$ depends on the slope before, γ , and after, κ , of the z_p parameter, which quantifies the turning point between the two power laws and identifies the peak of the CBC merger rate. The choice of parameters in this work is specified in Tab. 1 (see also App. B).

The distribution of BH mass is factorized in terms of comoving mass density, namely

$$\frac{dM_{\text{BH}}}{dz d\Omega} = \frac{dM_{\text{BH}}}{dV_c} \frac{dV_c}{dz d\Omega} = \rho_{\text{BH}}(z, \Omega) \frac{dV_c}{dz d\Omega}, \quad (7)$$

and using linear order perturbations, we can write

$$\rho_{\text{BH}}(z, \Omega) \approx \bar{\rho}_{\text{BH}} [1 + b_{\text{GW}}(1+z)^{\alpha_{\text{GW}}} \delta_{\text{DM}}(z, \Omega)]. \quad (8)$$

In the above equation, we have written the comoving density of available BHs in terms of an average density $\bar{\rho}_{\text{BH}}$, the DM density contrast $\delta_{\text{DM}}(z, \Omega)$ and multiplicative bias parameter parametrized as in Mukherjee et al. (2021); Diaz & Mukherjee (2022); Dalang & Baker (2024). Eq. 8 encapsulates the key physical assumption of the model: that the spatial distribution of the mergers is modulated by the underlying matter density field. The bias parameters ($b_{\text{GW}}, \alpha_{\text{GW}}$) encode how strongly and in what way the CBC merger rate traces the LSS (see for example Pedrotti et al. 2025).

In this exploratory work, we assume that GWs perfectly trace the DM distribution and therefore $b_{\text{GW}} = 1, \alpha_{\text{GW}} = 0$. In a more general scenario, we can still parametrize $b_{\text{H}}(z)$ and marginalize over its parameters' uncertainties.

Before proceeding, let us argue on how this method relates to current methodologies for dark sirens cosmology. If we combine Eq. 6 with Eq. 7 and Eq. 8, we can note that the usual binary black merger rate per comoving volume can be defined as $R_0 = R_{\text{BH}} \bar{\rho}_{\text{BH}}$. In this sense, R_0 is the merger rate for a homogenous universe. By further assuming that the universe is perfectly homogenous and isotropic ($\delta_{\text{DM}}(z, \Omega) = \delta_{\text{GW}}(z, \Omega) = 0$), then we can see that the rate in Eq. 5 collapses to the classical rate model used for dark sirens analyses (Mastrogiovanni et al. 2021, 2022, 2024).

In this work, we consider 3G GW detectors as they will probe compact binary mergers across a much larger redshift range than current instruments (Branchesi et al. 2023; Abac et al. 2026). In particular, the ET is expected to detect CBCs out to very high redshift, opening the possibility of tracing the cosmic expansion well beyond the local Universe. This makes 3G GW observatories particularly promising for standard siren cosmology. Specifically, we investigate the synergy between ET for the BBH detection on the gravitational side and SKAO.

In Fig. 1, we show the horizon for the ET observations compared to the SKAO reach in redshift. The horizon represents the maximum redshift for equal-mass, optimally oriented CBC GW sources observed with a threshold SNR. Here we compare the standard SNR = 8 threshold with the one we use throughout this work, i.e., SNR = 150. We used the triangular configuration for ET with the full cryogenic sensitivity curve as presented in Branchesi et al. (2023)⁴. The same configuration has been used in all the analyses presented in this paper.

We simulate 10^4 BBH events. For our choice of rate parameters for Eq. 6, this corresponds to one year of observations. Note that this is one order of magnitude less than the typical amount of observations per year expected for ET (Maggiore et al. 2020; Branchesi et al. 2023) as a consequence of rate parameters (see Tab. 1). Our choice was motivated by the need to concentrate the bulk of the events in the redshift range covered by the H_I maps, i.e. $z \in [0, \sim 3]$. In the following, we provide a brief description of how the parameters characterizing the GW events have been sampled. We refer to App. B for details.

We sample the masses uniformly in the detector frame⁵ in the mass range [$5M_\odot, 300M_\odot$]. Sky position and distance are chosen after the DM maps. All the other parameters are sampled uniformly in their range (see App. B and Tab. B1 therein for details). We then retain the subset of events that is detected by ET in its triangular configuration with the full cryogenic sensitivity curve as in Branchesi et al. (2023) with an SNR threshold of 150. The high SNR threshold is needed to ensure that our events are well-behaved under the Fisher analysis, which is used for their parameter estimation (PE). For each event, in fact, PE is performed in the Fisher-matrix approximation using GWFish (Dupletsa et al. 2023, 2025). To ensure the samples lie within their physical range, we post-processed the Fisher results with priors using sampling from the truncated multivariate Gaussian as described in Dupletsa et al. (2025). The resulting catalogs span a

⁴ The cryogenic curve for the 10 km ET is publicly available [here](#).

⁵ This is done for consistency in the hierarchical Bayesian analysis framework, see Sec. 2.4 for more details. We note that it implies a non-trivial mass distribution in the source frame. However, as no explicit mass-spectrum models are incorporated in our analysis, adopting a distribution that is uniform in detector-frame mass provides a convenient and practical assumption.

Figure 2. Sky maps of the H I density contrast and simulated GW event distributions at two representative redshifts. *Top panels:* Mollweide projections of the H I density contrast at $z \approx 0.04$ (left) and $z \approx 0.2$ (right). The yellow boxes indicate the sky region shown in the zoomed-in panels below. Color bars denote the amplitude of the density contrast. *Bottom panels:* Zoom-in of the boxed regions, comparing clustered GW events (left subpanels), which trace the underlying H I distribution, with isotropically distributed GW events (right subpanels). We increased the number of GW sources to 10k per map and the resolution of the map (using `nside=128`) for visualization purposes. While at low z the difference between clustered and isotropically distributed GW events is more pronounced, this distinction progressively diminishes at higher redshifts, where the two distributions become increasingly similar, according to the variation of the DM density contrast as shown in Fig. 3.

broad range of luminosity distances, and the 90% sky-localization areas generally increase with distance. Around 15% of events are localized on angular scales less than or comparable to the chosen map pixel area. Given the adopted Healpy pixelization (`nside=16`, see Sec.2.2), we broadly match the sky-localization precision of the simulated GW events (see App. B and Fig. B1 therein).

The maps of DM density contrast (see Section 2.1 for details) are used to populate the universe with GW sources using Eqs. 7 and 8. Since we want to probe the effect of clustering for GWs, we construct two catalogs of GW detections:

- (i) **Clustered GWs:** BBH events are distributed according to the same sky probability field traced by the DM maps.
- (ii) **Isotropic GWs:** BBH events are distributed uniformly in the sky, instead of explicitly following the DM clustering.

Under our choice of SNR threshold, this yields approximately 3100 detected events in both the clustered and isotropic scenarios. In Fig. 2, we show sample sky maps of the H I density contrast and simulated GW event distributions at two representative redshifts, low and relatively high: $z \approx 0.04$ (left panels) and $z \approx 0.2$ (right panels), respectively. The yellow boxes indicate the sky region shown in the zoomed-in panels below. In the zoomed insets, we compare clustered GW events (left subpanels), which trace the underlying DM distribution, with isotropically distributed GW events (right subpanels).

While at low z the difference between clustered and isotropically

distributed GW events is more pronounced, this distinction progressively diminishes at higher redshifts, where the two distributions become increasingly similar, according to the variation of the DM density contrast. These directional redshift-dependent fluctuations are the key ingredient to make the H I prior informative. For visualization purposes, a higher-resolution pixelization is used in the sky maps of Fig. 2. Additionally, we also increased the number of GW sources to 10k for each shown redshift slice.

2.4 The hierarchical Bayesian inference (HBI) framework

The aim of this work is to constrain cosmological parameters using GWs as *radio sirens*: we use the luminosity distance information coming from gravitational mock measurements and the redshift information from the simulations of H I maps. In order to do so, we work in the HBI framework. This is a two-level inference analysis combining posterior samples coming from individual GW events with population-level information.

Given N_{obs} GW events, collectively specified as $\{x\}$, each of which is described by its own set of parameters θ , the hierarchical likelihood that describes the probability of observing the specific dataset in a given time T_{obs} , and given the set of hyperparameters Λ , is (Mandel et al. 2019; Vitale et al. 2020; Mastrogiovanni et al. 2021, 2023,

Table 1. Uniform prior distributions adopted for the cosmological and rate parameters in the `icarogw` analysis. $\mathcal{U}[a, b]$ denotes a uniform distribution between a and b . The last column reports the injected values used in our simulations.

Parameter	Prior range	Injected value
H_0 [$\text{km s}^{-1} \text{Mpc}^{-1}$]	$\mathcal{U}[10, 240]$	67.7
$\Omega_{m,0}$	$\mathcal{U}[0.1, 0.9]$	0.308
γ	$\mathcal{U}[0, 12]$	2.7
κ	$\mathcal{U}[0, 12]$	6
z_p	$\mathcal{U}[0, 4]$	1

2024):

$$\mathcal{L}(\{x\}|\Lambda) \propto \exp[-N_{\text{exp}}(\Lambda)] \prod_{i=1}^{N_{\text{obs}}} T_{\text{obs}} \int \mathcal{L}_{\text{GW}}(x_i|\theta, \Lambda) \frac{dN_{\text{CBC}}}{d\tau d\theta}(\Lambda) d\theta, \quad (9)$$

where, we have the single-event likelihood $\mathcal{L}_{\text{GW}}(x_i|\theta, \Lambda)$ weighted by the population-level probability $\frac{dN_{\text{CBC}}}{d\tau d\theta}(\Lambda)$ term as explained in Eq. 5-8. The hyperparameters Λ govern the population-level model, describing the distribution of GW events as a function of redshift and sky position. In this study, we identify 5 population-level parameters that are detailed with their injection values and priors in Tab. 1.

Additionally, we have the term dependent on the expected number of events N_{exp} in the observing time interval T_{obs} . This term is necessary to properly account for GW selection effects. More details about this framework, and `icarogw`, the software tool used for this study, are given in [Mastrogiovanni et al. \(2023\)](#). Some details on the numerical implementation of the HBI framework in `icarogw` are also given in App. C.

The key assumption of our analysis is that in the modeling of the LoS redshift prior, we use the simulated H_I maps as the observable tracer of the DM field appearing in Eq. 8. We show the quantity $\rho_{\text{BH}}/\bar{\rho}_{\text{BH}}$ in Fig. 3 as a function of redshift for different directions. The variation is more pronounced at low redshift and becomes increasingly uniform toward higher redshift, approaching homogeneity by $z \sim 3$, the maximum redshift covered by the H_I maps. The apparent flattening at low redshifts is a binning artifact.

Conceptually, the *radio-siren* framework can be interpreted as a low spatial resolution generalization of galaxy-catalog dark sirens. Instead of assigning discrete host probabilities to resolved galaxies, we use the large-scale density field traced by H_I to construct a redshift prior along each line of sight. Using H_I maps instead of discrete galaxy catalogs circumvents issues associated with heterogeneous, flux-limited surveys and mitigates the completeness challenges inherent in standard dark-siren analyses.

Note that we neglect the impact of the source-frame mass. In other words, we are implicitly assuming that the detector distribution of source masses is uniform. Indeed, this is also the choice we made when generating GW events; there could have been the possibility of introducing a bias for the cosmological inference. Therefore, the individual GW events posterior samples of interest in our analysis are the luminosity distance and the sky position, namely RA and Dec. In this work, we deliberately did not use source-frame mass information in order to isolate the constraining power of the H_I redshift prior and avoid introducing dependence on a specific astrophysical mass model. Including the mass distribution, i.e., using spectral sirens, would provide an additional source of redshift information and could therefore improve cosmological constraints. However, it would also

Figure 3. Distribution of $\rho_{\text{BH}}/\bar{\rho}_{\text{BH}}$ along three different lines of sight identified by their right ascension RA and declination Dec (specified in the legend). The variation is more pronounced at low redshift and becomes increasingly uniform toward higher redshift, approaching homogeneity by $z \sim 3$, the maximum redshift covered by the H_I maps. The apparent flattening at low redshift is a binning artifact: the input redshift grid is sparse at low z .

introduce new potential systematics ([Mukherjee 2022](#); [Karathanasis et al. 2023](#); [Agarwal et al. 2025](#)).

3 RESULTS

The two GW catalogs (clustered and not), are analyzed either using or not the redshift information coming from the H_I maps. This comparison allows us to isolate the benefit of a correctly matched LSS prior and to test the bias introduced when the prior is inconsistent with the true source distribution.

3.1 Cosmology with Clustered GWs

Our main result is that including H_I information substantially improves the constraint on the posterior of H_0 when the GW events are clustered consistently with the underlying DM field. For the Clustered GWs - H_I case, we obtain

$$H_0 = 65.8_{-5.2}^{+4.9} \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1} \quad (10)$$

at 68% credibility, which represents a precision of $\sim 8\%$.

The result is shown in Fig. 4, which also reports the posterior on the other population parameters we considered in the analysis. The H_0 posterior is sharply peaked near the injected value, indicating that the H_I redshift prior carries sufficient information for the Hubble constant inference. By contrast, if the same clustered GW catalog is analyzed without H_I information, the Hubble-constant posterior is much broader. In this case, the posterior is close to uninformative. The comparison demonstrates that adding H_I information transforms a weak constraint into a meaningful cosmological measurement, corresponding to an improvement of $\sim 90\%$.

The constraints on $\Omega_{m,0}$ remain relatively weak even when H_I information is included. This reflects the limited sensitivity of the method to the shape of the distance–redshift relation beyond an overall scaling set by H_0 .

In terms of the other population parameters, we notice that in the case that H_I maps are used in the analyses, all injected values are properly recovered. Instead, if H_I maps are not included, and so the modeling of the LoS prior does not take into account the redshift information coming from H_I maps, then we might obtain a systematic bias in the estimation of k , z_p and γ . This systematic bias is introduced by the

Figure 4. Corner plot showing the marginalized posterior distributions and the 1σ and 2σ 2D confidence regions for the cosmological and rate parameters H_0 , $\Omega_{m,0}$, γ , κ , and z_p , inferred from clustered GW events. The dark purple contours correspond to the analysis including HI information (Clustered GWs - HI), while the light purple contours show the case without HI information (Clustered GWs - No HI). The injected fiducial values are indicated by magenta lines. The panels on the diagonal display the one-dimensional marginalized posteriors, with quoted median values and 68% credible intervals, highlighting the improvement in parameter constraints when HI data are included.

fact that the redshift distribution (number density) of GW sources strongly deviates from a uniform in comoving volume distribution, in particular for lower redshifts.

3.2 Cosmology with Isotropic GWs

We also consider what would happen in the case that GW events do not completely cluster as the DM field and are instead isotropically distributed in the sky. In this case, as well, we study what happens when, at the inference level, we include or do not include the HI prior. We show the result of this test in Fig. 5, where we compare with the clustered case. If the HI clustering prior is still used in this case, the inferred Hubble constant becomes biased towards higher values. If the isotropic catalog is analyzed without HI information, the constraint remains weak.

These results show that the clustering prior is only beneficial when it accurately reflects the true source distribution. Otherwise, it can systematically pull the inferred cosmology away from the injected value. If GWs are not clustered, and a HI map is used for the inference, then it is likely that we will overestimate the value of H_0 . This bias is introduced by the fact that, as GWs are uniform in the comoving volume, they are more likely to be placed at higher redshifts (higher H_0) as the HI maps are more uniform. This process introduces a high H_0 bias.

Figure 5. Posterior probability distributions for H_0 inferred from both clustered (Clustered GWs) and isotropically distributed (Isotropic GWs) GW events under two scenarios: with HI information included (HI) and without HI information (No HI). The vertical line indicates the injected value of H_0 .

This result highlights a key systematic risk of the method: the inferred cosmology is conditional on the assumed clustering model. If the true GW population deviates from the assumed bias relation, the redshift prior becomes misspecified, leading to biased cosmological

inference. This underscores the need to jointly model cosmology and source clustering.

This case gives us a warning: if in the Universe, due to astrophysical effects, the H_I field is not a good tracer for the GW distribution, the *radio-siren* method could give biased results. On sufficiently large scales, however, our main assumption should hold.

3.3 Validation test of the clustering of GW sources

An important consistency test of the pipeline is to simultaneously constrain the clustering properties of the GW source population as in Eq. 8. In particular, the bias parameters ($b_{\text{GW}}, \alpha_{\text{GW}}$) encode how BBH mergers trace the underlying matter distribution.

In Fig. 6, we explored this possibility by allowing these parameters to vary together with the other cosmological parameters. We find that we are able to recover the injected values within uncertainties, indicating that the method is self-consistent. Also, the posterior on H_0 is not affected by enlarging the number of population parameters we are doing inference on.

To illustrate how the bias parameters affect the GW distribution along the line of sight, we show, in Fig. 7, how the BH density contrast $\rho_{\text{BH}}/\bar{\rho}_{\text{BH}}$ evolves for different choices of ($b_{\text{GW}}, \alpha_{\text{GW}}$). Fixing a representative sky direction, we observe that increasing the bias amplitude enhances the contrast between overdense and underdense regions, effectively sharpening the redshift-dependent structure traced by the GW population.

When a redshift-dependent bias is introduced ($\alpha_{\text{GW}} \neq 0$), the modulation becomes progressively stronger at higher redshift, leading to an amplification of fluctuations where the underlying matter field is otherwise more homogeneous. This behavior reflects the parametrization in Eq. 8, where the bias enters as a multiplicative factor of the density contrast.

From the perspective of the *radio-siren* framework, these effects directly translate into changes in the informativeness of the redshift prior. A stronger or evolving bias increases the contrast along the LoS, potentially improving the localization of GW events in redshift space. However, it also introduces additional modeling dependence: if the assumed bias does not match the true clustering properties of the source population, the inferred redshift prior may become misspecified, leading to biased cosmological constraints.

3.4 Constraints on $H(z)$

Although the main focus of this work is the Hubble constant, the same posterior samples can be propagated to reconstruct the late-time expansion history over the redshift range covered by the H_I maps. Assuming a flat Λ CDM background, the expansion rate is obtained from the inferred cosmological parameters as:

$$H(z) = H_0 \sqrt{\Omega_{\text{m},0}(1+z)^3 + 1 - \Omega_{\text{m},0}} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 8 shows the posterior predictive reconstruction of $H(z)/(1+z)$ as a function of redshift, comparing the Clustered GWs - H_I and the Clustered GWs - No H_I analyses. The shaded regions correspond to the 68% (darker shade) and 95% (lighter shade) credible intervals, while the prior predictive distribution is also shown for reference (black lines).

The inclusion of H_I information leads to a substantial tightening of the reconstructed expansion history, particularly at low redshift ($z \lesssim 0.5$), where the density contrast of the H_I field is highest and the redshift prior is most informative. In this regime, the posterior predictive band for the Clustered GWs - H_I case closely traces the

injected cosmology, with a significant reduction in uncertainty relative to the prior and to the Clustered GWs - No H_I. This reflects the improved constraint on H_0 , which sets the overall normalization of the expansion rate.

At intermediate redshifts ($0.5 \lesssim z \lesssim 2$), the reconstruction remains consistent with the fiducial model, although the uncertainty gradually increases. Toward the highest redshifts probed by the H_I maps ($z \sim 3$), the posterior predictive distribution broadens and approaches the prior envelope, indicating that the data carry limited information on the detailed shape of $H(z)$ in this regime. This is consistent with the relatively weak constraints on $\Omega_{\text{m},0}$ observed in Fig. 4, and highlights that the current setup primarily constrains the normalization of the expansion history rather than its evolution.

Overall, these results show that the *radio-siren* method not only constrains H_0 , but also enables a consistent reconstruction of the late-time expansion history over the redshift range $z \in [0, \sim 3]$. While the sensitivity to the detailed redshift evolution remains limited in the present configuration, future analyses with larger GW catalogs and more realistic H_I modeling may allow for competitive constraints on $H(z)$ beyond a simple normalization measurement.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

We have presented a proof-of-concept study of *radio sirens*, a joint cosmological framework that combines BBH standard sirens with H_I IM. The central idea is that, in the absence of EM counterparts, the LSS traced by H_I can be used as a redshift prior for dark sirens. Using simulated ET BBH events and mock SKA-Mid-like H_I maps, we find that this additional information dramatically improves cosmological inference when the source population is clustered consistently with the underlying H_I field.

Our fiducial clustered analysis yields a constraint on H_0 at the $\sim 8\%$ level, improving by $\sim 90\%$ with respect to the corresponding Clustered GWs - No H_I case, which is largely uninformative. This demonstrates that tomographic 21 cm maps can be used for dark siren cosmology: a physically motivated redshift prior that exploits the three-dimensional structure of the Universe. The method is especially promising in the ET era, when the number of BBH detections will be sufficiently large to enable population-level inference out to cosmological distances (Branchesi et al. 2023; Abac et al. 2026).

At the same time, our isotropic-source tests highlight an important caveat. If the GW source population does not follow the matter distribution in the way assumed by the prior, then the H_I-informed analysis can introduce substantial bias. This means that future applications of the *radio-siren* analysis must rely on realistic astrophysical models for BBH environments and clustering.

Additionally, several simplifying assumptions made here should be relaxed in future work. To begin with, we have assumed that the H_I field traces the underlying matter density without additional bias or stochasticity. At the single GW-event analysis, we relied on the Fisher matrix approximation, even though enhanced through the inclusion of a simplified version of priors (Dupletsa et al. 2025).

Another important extension of the present analysis would concern the inclusion of the BBH mass spectrum. A realistic implementation should jointly model the mass spectrum, the BBH merger-rate evolution, and the clustering relation between GW sources and the H_I density field.

Finally, our treatment neglects observational complications in IM, such as beam effects, foreground removal, calibration systematics, and the detailed response of SKA-Mid. A more realistic end-to-end analysis should also include these effects.

Figure 6. Results for the headline results with Clustered GWs - Hi including the two parameters entering the bias parametrization: b_{GW} and α_{GW} . The injected fiducial values are indicated with magenta lines.

Figure 7. LoS evolution of the BH mass density contrast, $\rho_{\text{BH}}/\bar{\rho}_{\text{BH}}$, as a function of redshift for a fixed sky direction ($\text{RA} = 150^\circ$, $\text{Dec} = 30^\circ$), under different assumptions for the GW bias parameters. The baseline case ($b_{\text{GW}} = 1$, $\alpha_{\text{GW}} = 0$) corresponds to GW sources tracing the underlying matter field without additional redshift dependence. Increasing the bias amplitude ($b_{\text{GW}} = 2$) enhances the contrast of overdense and underdense regions, while introducing a redshift-dependent bias ($\alpha_{\text{GW}} = 2$) further amplifies fluctuations at higher redshift.

Despite these limitations, the present study establishes the basic viability of the *radio-siren* concept. With the large BBH catalogs expected from 3G detectors and the tomographic reach of future 21 cm surveys, the joint ET-SKA approach could become a powerful and independent route to precision cosmology.

An additional advantage of the *radio-siren* framework concerns the treatment of selection effects and completeness. In traditional galaxy-catalog dark-siren analyses, the redshift prior relies on discrete galaxy samples, often combined from different surveys and inherently flux-limited. This requires careful modeling of catalog incompleteness, typically through assumptions on the galaxy luminosity function and the evaluation of the number of missing galaxies as a function of redshift. Such corrections introduce both statistical uncertainty and potential systematic biases, especially at higher redshifts where incompleteness becomes severe.

In contrast, the use of Hi intensity mapping significantly simplifies this aspect. Since the observable is a finely redshift-spaced tracer of the underlying matter density field, rather than a catalog of individually detected sources, the need for explicit completeness corrections is largely removed. At leading order, the redshift prior can be constructed assuming a distribution uniform in comoving volume, whenever the information from Hi density contrast is not available. This advantage becomes even more important at high red-

Figure 8. Posterior predictive constraints on $H(z)/(1+z)$ as a function of redshift z . The shaded bands show the 68% (darker shade) and 95% (lighter shade) credible intervals for Clustered GWs - H_I (in purple) and for Clustered GWs - No H_I (in pink). The solid magenta line indicates the injected cosmological model. For comparison, the black lines represent the prior predictive distribution (68%–95% credible intervals).

shift. While galaxy-catalog dark-siren analyses become increasingly limited by catalog incompleteness and heterogeneous survey selection functions, H_I intensity mapping provides a tomographic tracer of the LSS over large cosmological volumes. This is particularly relevant for next-generation detectors, where the combination of large volumes and high redshift coverage would otherwise make completeness corrections increasingly challenging and model-dependent.

Overall, *radio sirens* should be viewed as an additional source of information. Galaxy catalogs provide discrete host-galaxy information, but become increasingly limited by completeness and survey-selection effects at high redshift. The BBH mass spectrum can provide additional statistical redshift information, but requires careful modeling of astrophysical evolution and of possible redshift dependence in the source population. H_I intensity mapping supplies a spectroscopic tracer of the LSS over large cosmological volumes that is not completeness-limited, as the full H_I mass function is sampled in the measured temperature brightness of each pixel. This makes it particularly well matched to the high-redshift reach of third-generation GW detectors. Combining these ingredients in a joint framework will be essential to exploit the full potential of BBH standard sirens, while controlling the associated astrophysical, observational, and population-modeling systematics.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The data products, samples of the GW events, the injection set and the H_I maps, are available on Zenodo (upon publication of this paper). Tutorials on their generation and usage are included. Link to H_I branch of icarogw.

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APPENDIX A: ADDITIONAL VALIDATION TESTS

We performed two additional validation tests for both the Isotropic GWs - HI and Clustered GWs - HI analyses discussed in the main text.

First, we revisited the Isotropic GWs - HI case by comparing the analysis based on Fisher-matrix parameter-estimation uncertainties with an idealized setup in which the GW events are assumed to be perfectly measured. The result is shown in Fig. A1. The posterior remains biased when the HI prior is included even in the perfect-PE limit, demonstrating that the dominant source of the shift is not measurement noise, but rather the mismatch between the assumed clustering prior and the true source distribution. In other words, if the BBH population does not trace the matter field while the inference model assumes that it does, the redshift prior is misspecified and the cosmological posterior is shifted accordingly.

Interestingly, measurement errors on the GW side help the H_0 posterior to shift towards the injected value. Once the single-event likelihoods are broadened in luminosity distance and sky position, the posterior support is distributed over a wider region of the redshift prior, which slightly reduces the tendency of the analysis to concentrate probability at the highest redshifts allowed by the nearly homogeneous HI maps. This explains why the biased posterior obtained with Fisher uncertainties is somewhat closer to the injected value than in the perfect-PE case.

Second, we tested the robustness of the headline Clustered GWs - HI result against fluctuations in the source catalog. To do so, we

Figure A1. Posterior probability distributions for H_0 inferred from isotropically distributed (Isotropic GWs) GW events under two with Hi information included (Hi) at the analysis stage. We show the results with perfectly measured GWs and including PE errors. The vertical line indicates the injected value of H_0 .

Figure A2. Posterior probability distributions for H_0 inferred from clustered GW events with Hi information included, under different GW events distribution realizations. The vertical line indicates the injected value of H_0 .

generated several independent realizations of the clustered GW population. Figure A2 shows that the recovered H_0 posterior is stable across realizations: all runs exhibit a dominant peak close to the injected value, with only moderate realization-to-realization scatter. A subset of the realizations additionally shows a secondary peak extending toward higher H_0 , indicating that finite-sample fluctuations can still produce some multi-modality at the catalog size considered here. Overall, these tests support the conclusion that the main qualitative behavior discussed in Sec. 3 is not driven by a single lucky or pathological realization.

APPENDIX B: SIMULATION OF THE BBH EVENTS

We generate a synthetic population of BBH mergers assuming the merger-rate model introduced in Sec. 2.3. The fiducial cosmology is fixed to the values reported in Tab. 1, namely $H_0 = 67.7 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ and $\Omega_{m,0} = 0.308$, while the redshift evolution of the source-frame rate is described by the modified Madau–Dickinson parameters $\gamma = 2.7$, $\kappa = 6$, and $z_p = 1$. These values were chosen to place a substantial fraction of the detectable population within the redshift interval covered by the Hi maps, rather than maximizing the

Table B1. List of the prior distribution for the parameters describing a GW event used to generate the starting datasets. For a definition of the listed parameters, see Tab. 4 in Dupletsa et al. (2025). Note that here we provide information on the redshift distribution, whereas at the GW PE level we use the luminosity distance. The corresponding luminosity distance values are obtained from the redshift assuming our injected cosmology as in Tab. 1.

parameter	units	prior	prior range
m_1	M_\odot	Uniform	[5, 300]
m_2	M_\odot	Uniform	[5, 300]
z	[Mpc]	Uniform in source-frame + Madau-Dickinson (+Hi)	[0, ~ 3]
θ_{JN}	[rad]	Sine	[0, π]
Dec	[rad]	Cosine	$[-\frac{\pi}{2}, +\frac{\pi}{2}]$
RA	[rad]	Uniform	[0, 2π]
ϕ	[rad]	Uniform	[0, 2π]
Ψ	[rad]	Uniform	[0, π]
t_c	[s]	Delta	0.
a_1	-	Uniform	[0, 0.99]
a_2	-	Uniform	[0, 0.99]
tilt ₁	[rad]	Sine	[0, π]
tilt ₂	[rad]	Sine	[0, π]
phi ₁₂	[rad]	Uniform	[0, 2π]
phi _{JL}	[rad]	Uniform	[0, 2π]

total number of ET detections. For this reason, the catalog contains fewer events than would be expected in a fully realistic one-year ET forecast (e.g. Branchesi et al. 2023; Abac et al. 2026), but it is better matched to the science target of this study.

We simulate 10^4 BBH mergers, corresponding to one year of observations for the adopted rate normalization. Sky position and distance are assigned using the mock LSS information. In the clustered catalog, events are distributed according to the density-modulated merger-rate field of Eqs. 6 and 8, so that BBH mergers trace the same underlying DM structures. In the isotropic catalog, by contrast, the clustering term is switched off, and the sources are distributed uniformly in comoving volume. The two catalogs, therefore, share the same detector setup and selection effects, but differ only in whether they explicitly follow the DM distribution. All the other binary parameters are sampled from isotropic or uniform distributions over their physical ranges as detailed in Tab. B1.

The generated events are passed through `GWFish` using ET in its triangular configuration and the full cryogenic sensitivity curve Branchesi et al. (2023). Even though we retain only the events with a SNR greater than 150, an unconstrained multivariate Gaussian approximation can place posterior support outside the physical parameter domain, for example, at negative luminosity distance or outside the allowed angular ranges. To avoid this, we post-process the Fisher covariance by drawing samples from a truncated multivariate Gaussian, following the procedure described in Dupletsa et al. (2025). This step preserves the local Fisher information while enforcing the physical priors required by the hierarchical analysis. We apply uniform cuts in the ranges detailed in Tab. B1, except for the masses and distance, where we impose a positivity requirement only.

The posterior samples produced in this way are then used as input to `icarogw`. For each event, the relevant information entering the population analysis is the luminosity distance and sky position (RA and Dec) samples. Fig. B1 summarizes the localization properties of the detected sample of GW events by showing the luminosity distance versus sky localization area. Here we report the headline Clustered GWs - Hi results which contain ~ 3100 detected GW events (the events simulated for the Isotropic GWs - Hi scenario present analogous distance-sky location distribution). Each point represents a

Figure B1. Luminosity distance versus sky localization area for the ~ 3100 detected GW events in the clustered GWs case. Each point represents a detected event, plotted as a function of luminosity distance (bottom axis) and corresponding redshift (top axis). The vertical axis shows the 90% credible sky localization area, $\Delta\Omega_{90\%}$, in deg^2 . Horizontal lines indicate the pixel area of the map ($\sim 13 \text{ deg}^2$) and multiples thereof ($10\times$ and $100\times$) for reference. The plot illustrates the general trend of increasing localization uncertainty with distance (and redshift).

detected event, plotted as a function of luminosity distance and corresponding redshift. The vertical axis shows the 90% credible sky localization area, $\Delta\Omega_{90\%}$, in deg^2 . The sky localization has been computed from the Fisher samples with prior cuts, with n_{side} progressively increased from 64 to 2048 for increasingly well-localized GW events. Horizontal lines indicate the pixel area of the map ($\sim 13 \text{ deg}^2$) and multiples thereof ($10\times$ and $100\times$) for reference. The plot illustrates the general trend of increasing localization uncertainty with distance (and redshift).

APPENDIX C: BREAKING DOWN HIERARCHICAL BAYESIAN INFERENCE AND ITS NUMERICAL IMPLEMENTATION IN ICAROGW

The hierarchical analysis is performed with `icarogw`, which evaluates the population likelihood by Monte Carlo reweighting of both posterior samples and injections Mastrogiovanni et al. (2024). Since the single-event likelihood $\mathcal{L}_{\text{GW}}(x_i | \theta, \Lambda)$ is not directly available, the event term in Eq. (9) is estimated from posterior samples by undoing the prior used in the parameter-estimation stage. Denoting by $N_{s,i}$ the number of posterior samples for event i , one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} \int \mathcal{L}_{\text{GW}}(x_i | \theta, \Lambda) \frac{dN_{\text{CBC}}}{d\theta}(\Lambda) d\theta &\sim \frac{1}{N_{s,i}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{s,i}} \frac{1}{\pi(\theta_{i,j} | \Lambda)} \frac{dN_{\text{CBC}}}{d\theta}(\Lambda) |_{i,j} \\ &\equiv \frac{1}{N_{s,i}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{s,i}} w_{i,j} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C1})$$

where $\pi(\theta_{i,j} | \Lambda)$ is the prior used to obtain the posterior samples.

Selection effects are treated in an analogous way using the injection set. If N_{gen} is the total number of simulated injections and N_{det} the number of injections that pass the detection threshold, the expected

Figure C1. Posterior probability distributions for H_0 inferred from clustered GW events with Hi information included (Hi), under two different numerical stability checks: $N_{\text{eff,PE}}$ and $N_{\text{eff,inj}}$. The vertical line indicates the injected (true) value of H_0 .

number of detections can be estimated as:

$$\begin{aligned} N_{\text{exp}} &= T_{\text{obs}} \int p_{\text{det}}(\theta) \frac{dN_{\text{CBC}}}{d\theta}(\Lambda) d\theta \\ &\sim \frac{T_{\text{obs}}}{N_{\text{gen}}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{det}}} \frac{1}{\pi_{\text{inj}}(\theta_j)} \frac{dN_{\text{CBC}}}{d\theta} |_j \\ &\equiv \frac{T_{\text{obs}}}{N_{\text{gen}}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{det}}} s_j \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C2})$$

where $\pi_{\text{inj}}(\theta_j)$ is the prior used to generate the *injections*.

The final numerical expression for Eq. (9), as computed in `icarogw`, is given by:

$$\ln \mathcal{L}(\{x\} | \Lambda) \sim -\frac{T_{\text{obs}}}{N_{\text{gen}}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{det}}} s_j + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{obs}}} \ln \left[\frac{T_{\text{obs}}}{N_{s,i}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{s,i}} w_{i,j} \right] \quad (\text{C3})$$

A useful way to assess the numerical robustness of this Monte-Carlo estimate is through effective-sample-size diagnostics. For the reweighted posterior samples of a single event i we define:

$$N_{\text{eff,PE}}^{(i)} = \frac{\left(\sum_j w_{i,j} \right)^2}{\sum_j w_{i,j}^2}, \quad (\text{C4})$$

which measures how many posterior samples contribute effectively after reweighting Talbot & Golomb (2023). Likewise, for the injection term, we define:

$$N_{\text{eff,inj}} = \frac{\left(\sum_j^{N_{\text{det}}} s_j \right)^2}{\sum_j^{N_{\text{det}}} s_j^2 - \frac{1}{N_{\text{gen}}} \left(\sum_j^{N_{\text{det}}} s_j \right)^2}. \quad (\text{C5})$$

which quantifies the effective support of the injection set in the region of hyper-parameter space favored by the analysis.

In Fig. C1 we compare the reference Clustered GWs - Hi analysis with runs in which we explicitly monitor the impact of these two diagnostics. The posterior on H_0 remains consistent across the different choices, indicating that the headline result is not driven by a numerical pathology of the reweighting procedure.

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